

Synthesis of polymer-supported Zn(II) as a novel and green nanocatalyst for promoting click reactions and using design of experiment for optimization of reaction conditions

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Abstract

A novel, highly stable and green ZnCl₂ nanoparticles (NPs) of modified poly(styrene-co-maleic anhydride) (SMA) was prepared by a simple procedure and was used to investigate the efficiency of the Click reaction. In this regard, SMA was modified with 3-aminopyridine to obtain the corresponding poly(styrene-co-maleimide) (SMI). ZnCl₂ was immobilized onto SMI as NPs. The obtained Zn(II)-SMI nanocatalyst was characterized using various techniques including FTIR, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, scanning electron microscope image, thermogravimetric analysis and inductively coupled plasma. The catalytic activity of aforementioned NPs was successfully tested in the regioselective synthesis of 1,4-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole. On the other hand, the design of experiment was used as a systematic method to optimize the reaction condition. Programing shows that the optimum reaction temperature and amount of catalyst are 96 °C and 0.05 g, respectively.

Keywords: Zn(II)-SMI, nanocatalyst, 1,4-disubstitued 1,2,3-triazole, Click reaction, green chemistry